

Empirical Comparison of Prim's and Kruskal's Algorithms in Python Using Array-Based and DSU Implementations

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Abstract

The Minimum Spanning Tree (MST) problem is a well-known problem in graph theory. Prim's and Kruskal's algorithms are both efficient in theory, but their actual performance depends a lot on how they are implemented and also on the programming language used.

In this paper, I compare a heap-based implementation of Prim's algorithm with two versions of Kruskal's algorithm in Python: one using Disjoint Set Union (DSU) and another using a simple array-based component tracking method.

Experiments were done on both dense and sparse random graphs. The results show clear differences in running time, mainly because of how data structures are handled in Python.

1 Introduction

The Minimum Spanning Tree (MST) problem is about finding a subset of edges in a weighted graph that connects all vertices with the minimum possible total weight.

There are two commonly used algorithms:

- Prim's algorithm
- Kruskal's algorithm

Even though both have good theoretical time complexity, their actual performance in Python can vary because of interpreter overhead and how data structures are used. This work studies those differences using experiments.

2 Related Work

The MST problem has been studied for many years in graph theory and algorithms. Standard results and proofs are available in textbooks like Cormen et al. [1].

Prim's algorithm works well when implemented with a priority queue. Kruskal's algorithm is usually preferred for sparse graphs and works by sorting edges and using a Disjoint Set Union (DSU) structure. DSU with path compression is known to be very efficient in practice [2].

Previous studies also show that in real programming languages like Python, actual runtime can differ from theoretical complexity because of interpreter overhead, memory usage patterns, and built-in optimizations like Timsort.

3 Theoretical Background and Time Complexity

3.1 Prim's Algorithm

Prim's algorithm builds the MST step by step by always picking the smallest edge that connects a visited node to an unvisited node.

Time Complexity:

- With binary heap: $O(E \log V)$
- With simple array search: $O(V^2 + E)$

3.2 Kruskal's Algorithm (DSU)

Kruskal's algorithm sorts all edges first and then picks edges one by one, making sure no cycle is formed using DSU.

Time Complexity:

- Sorting edges: $O(E \log E)$
- DSU operations: almost $O(1)$ per operation (amortized)
- Total: $O(E \log E)$

3.3 Kruskal's Algorithm (Array-Based)

This version uses simple sets to track components instead of DSU. When two components are joined, all elements are updated.

Time Complexity:

- Worst case: $O(E \cdot V)$

4 Algorithms Overview

4.1 Prim's Algorithm

- Uses a priority queue in the optimized version
- Keeps track of visited nodes

4.2 Kruskal's Algorithm (Standard)

- Sorts edges by weight
- Uses DSU to avoid cycles

4.3 Kruskal's Algorithm (Variant)

- Uses simple sets instead of DSU
- Merges sets manually when needed

5 Implementation Details

5.1 Graph Generation

- Dense graphs: complete graphs
- Sparse graphs: start with a spanning tree and add extra edges
- Edge weights are random integers

5.2 Experimental Setup

- Language used: Python 3
- Timing function: `time.perf_counter_ns()`
- Each test is run 5 times and averaged
- Number of vertices: 2 to 500

6 Results

Both Prim's and Kruskal's algorithms produced the same MST weight, so correctness is confirmed.

Figure 1: Comparison of execution time of MST algorithms in Python. Prim (original) uses a heap-based method, while Prim (variant) uses linear search. Kruskal (original) uses DSU, and Kruskal (variant) uses array-based component tracking. Results are averaged over multiple runs for different graph sizes.

7 Discussion

7.1 Interpreter Overhead

Python loops and heap operations add extra overhead, especially in Prim's implementation.

7.2 Sorting Efficiency

Kruskal's algorithm benefits from Python's very optimized sorting (Timsort).

7.3 Memory Behavior

Array-based methods sometimes use memory better but become slow when merging large sets.

7.4 Prim Variant Behavior

The array-based version of Prim becomes slower because it checks all nodes to find the minimum, making it $O(V^2)$.

8 Conclusion

This study shows that real performance of MST algorithms in Python depends a lot on how they are implemented.

Even if two algorithms have similar theoretical complexity, their actual runtime can be very different because of data structures and language behavior.

9 Future Work

- Improve DSU with rank and path compression
- Test on larger graphs
- Compare with C++ implementations
- Add statistical analysis like variance and confidence intervals

References

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